

Research Software Alliance

2025 Community Report

In 2025, the [Research Software Alliance \(ReSA\)](#) deepened its impact on the global research ecosystem, bringing together a diverse international community of [stakeholders](#) to advance the recognition of research software and the people behind it as essential to research. Working in close collaboration with decision-makers and key influencers worldwide, we helped drive a more connected, sustainable, and resilient landscape. A major highlight of the year was the launch of our [2025–2028 Strategic Plan](#), setting a clear direction for the next phase of growth and reinforcing our commitment to positioning research software as a fundamental, first-class research output. We're delighted to highlight key achievements from 2025 and set the stage for our priorities in 2026 and beyond.

Advancing research software policy

A key area of focus in 2025 was advancing research software policy at the international level. We played a leading role in shaping international policy conversations. Contributions to initiatives such as the OECD workshop on [Access to Research Software: Opportunities and Challenges](#) (read more in our [blog post](#)) enabled advancements in international policy initiatives. At the institutional policy level, our work co-leading efforts to identify gaps in research software policy through the joint ReSA and [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\) Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\) Working Group](#), supported by [RDA TIGER funding](#), helped identify critical gaps. This work expanded the [research software policy database](#), informed institutional guidance, and supported workshops at international conferences to increase policy adoption. A key output was the publication of the report [Identifying Gaps in Research Software Policy](#), which establishes a common framework and highlights areas where institutional policy development is still needed.

Strengthening the global community and supporting action

Community-building remained central to our work, marked by significant expansion of our forums. In addition to the success of the [Research Software Funders Forum](#) and its working groups, we continued the [Research Software Infrastructure \(RSI\) Forum](#) and launched new forums for [policymakers](#), [publishers](#), [skills and training](#), and [metascience](#). As secretariat for the [International Council of RSE Associations](#), we supported a growing global network of national and regional organisations.

To strengthen cross-sector collaboration, we launched the [Research Software Community Leadership Forum \(CLF\)](#). Global nominations opened in July, with the forum formally established in November. The CLF brings together elected representatives from ReSA's stakeholder forums, in addition to openly nominated members from underrepresented groups. Together, these forums and the CLF are becoming key mechanisms for aligning stakeholders and driving coordinated action across the research software landscape.

ReSA [task forces](#) continued to play a key role in 2025, enabling the global community to identify shared challenges and develop practical, internationally relevant solutions across priority areas. Bringing together stakeholders from across sectors, these groups translate community expertise into coordinated action and tangible outputs.

The [Actionable FAIR4RS task force](#) exemplifies this approach. At USRSE'25 in October, [Bhavesh Patel shared progress on the task force's work](#) to develop practical guidelines for making research software Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). Since its launch in December 2024, the task force has advanced through focused subgroups combining literature review and community input, with outputs expected in 2026 to support improved software reuse and alignment with funder and institutional expectations.

In late 2025, the [Succession Planning for Research Software task force](#) was established as a joint initiative with [CURIOSS](#). This task force aims to provide a best practices guide for responsibly wrapping up research code when individuals leave their institutions, addressing a common challenge faced across the international research software community.

Expanding partnerships and global engagement

We strengthened our global network in 2025 by welcoming new [Organisational Members](#) and collaborating with international partners. ReSA, the RDA, and [Red Latinoamericana y de España de Ciencia Abierta \(LA Referencia\)](#) convened a [webinar series](#) exploring research software, research data, and open science in Latin America and the Caribbean. The series brought together research software engineers (RSEs), researchers, policymakers, data stewards, and other experts to discuss key issues [shaping the future of open science across the region](#).

We contributed to key international events in 2025, including [International Data Week \(IDW\) 2025](#), [RSECon25](#), and [New Zealand Research Software Engineering Conference](#). As a [co-located event](#) during IDW 2025, [we hosted a half-day hybrid workshop on supporting research software in research policy and funding programs](#). Designed for funders and policymakers, the workshop provided practical strategies for recognising and integrating research software into funding initiatives, understanding existing investments, and strengthening policy frameworks that support both software and the people who develop it.

In September, at RSECon25, we announced the inaugural [International Research Software Conference \(IRSC\)](#), to be held 7–8 September 2026 in Sheffield, UK, with remote participation, co-located with [RSECon26](#). The conference will bring together global leaders to advance strategic coordination, long-term sustainability, and high-level collaboration across the research software community. It builds on earlier scoping work supported by the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation (grant 2024-22426), which explored community-supported approaches to convening an international conference through an options paper, [Towards an International Research Software Conference](#), and a [community consultation](#). In 2025, this work progressed through dedicated [committees](#), leading to the establishment of a [committee](#) to implement the recommendations from our report.

Image credits: Michelle Barker, Daniel S. Katz, Bhavesh Patel

Staying connected

We continued to ensure broad dissemination of opportunities and updates through our monthly [newsletter](#) and active engagement across our [Slack workspace](#) and social media platforms, including [LinkedIn](#), [Mastodon](#), and [Bluesky](#), helping to connect and grow the global research software community.

Looking ahead

At the end of 2025, we secured \$240K in funding from Schmidt Sciences to support a project on research software engineering in the age of generative AI. This work is already underway in 2026, including a [workshop in Edinburgh](#) in March that brought

together stakeholders to develop a roadmap for how research software will be produced in the age of generative AI, independent of today's specific roles or job titles, reflecting our continued commitment to international coordination.

Moreover, early efforts have focused on advancing priorities from the 2025–2028 Strategic Plan, deepening engagement across stakeholder forums, and progressing plans for IRSC26.

Join ReSA

Get involved and make an impact by:

- Joining [task forces](#) focused on key challenges and solutions
- Staying informed through our regular, curated [newsletter](#)
- Becoming an [Organisational Member](#), [supporting a task force](#), [collaborating with us](#), or making a [donation](#)
- Getting involved in the [International Research Software Conference](#)
- Raising awareness of the critical role of software in research by sharing ReSA [resources](#)
- [Signing or supporting](#) the [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#) (ADORE.software)
- Connecting with the community on [LinkedIn](#), [Bluesky](#), and [Mastodon](#), or at our [events](#)
- Joining the ReSA [Slack](#) to collaborate with decision-makers and key influencers
- [Contributing resources](#) and [guidelines](#); ideas for [task forces](#), [events](#), and [news](#); or if you have other ideas for ReSA, then [let us know](#).

We look forward to welcoming you!

Acknowledgments

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ReSA is supported by the community through Organisational and Founding Members, project grants, task force and forum support, collaborations, and donations. An [overview](#) of ReSA income and expenditures is available online. Our grants are also available on [Open Grants](#).